

Multi-Attribute Decision Making for Smog Control Using Extended Vector Similarity Measure Based on Interval Type-2 Intuitionistic Fuzzy Sets

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Abstract. Interval Type-2 Intuitionistic Fuzzy Sets (IT2IFS) serve an essential part in the theory of fuzzy sets, serving to be models for linguistic phrases and finding applications in engineering. These sets are described through their Footprints of Uncertainty (FOU), that are further characterized through functions of membership (MF) and non-membership functions (NMF). Uncertainty within the set is quantified by the IT2IFS centroid. When employing IT2IFS to model input words in a CWW engine (Zadeh 1996, 1999; Mendel 2002; Liu and Mendel 2009), the engine's output is also an IT2IFS, requiring mapping to a linguistic label for comprehension. Since each linguistic label is represented by an IT2IFS, it becomes essential to assess the similarity between the CWW engine's output and linguistic labels to identify the most analogous linguistic label. This paper aims to introduce the concept of the IT2IFS centroid and utilize it for comparing two IT2IFS using vector similarity measure (VSM).

Keywords: Interval Type-2 Intuitionistic Fuzzy Sets (IT2IFS); Centroid; Extended vector similarity measure (EVSM); Multi-attribute decision making (MADM).

1. Introduction

One of the most popular and useful techniques for managing non-probabilistic uncertainty is fuzzy set theory. L.A. Zadeh introduced fuzzy sets (Zadeh 1965), which have several practical

applications and allow for easier modeling of complicated systems. The modeling of T1FS gets increasingly complicated when more uncertainties are introduced. In order to capture the fuzziness and uncertainty of real-world problems, Mendel and John (Mendel and John 2002; Mendel et al. 2006; Mendel 2007) presented T2FS, these incorporate a footprint of uncertainty that adds more degrees of freedom and allow one to characterize the uncertain data in a three-dimensional (3D) representation. The most often used T2FS, IT2FS (Mendel and John 2002; Mendel et al. 2006; Mendel 2007), is an a typical example of general T2FS and is less complex due to the large figures of complexity involved. Touqeer et al. (2020, 2021) have worked significantly with IT2FS.

IFS (Atanassov 1986, 1989), an extension of fuzzy sets, are introduced by K. T. Atanassov. In an IFS, an element's membership degree represents the level of membership, as in fuzzy sets. However, there is an additional degree called non-membership degree, which quantifies the level of an element's non-membership in the set. In order to address the vagueness of incomplete and unclear knowledge or information, IFS are beneficial and helpful in decision-making difficulties by numerous researchers.

IT2IFS have emerged as fundamental constructs in the realm of fuzzy set theory, playing a pivotal role in modeling linguistic expressions and finding diverse applications in engineering domains. The distinctive features of these sets are their FOU, which are defined by UMF, LMF, UNMF and LMF. Quantification of ambiguity within an IT2IFS is encapsulated by its centroid, contributing to a nuanced understanding of the inherent imprecision in linguistic modeling. Particularly, when applied to model input words within a Computing with Words (CWW) engine, the engine's output manifests as an IT2IFS. This necessitates the mapping of the engine's output to a linguistic label for comprehensibility. Given that each linguistic label is represented by an IT2IFS, evaluating the similarity between the CWW engine's output and linguistic labels becomes imperative for identifying the most analogous linguistic label.

MADM (Touqeer et al. 2021,2023) is a crucial procedure in various fields, ranging from business and engineering to healthcare and environmental management. It entails assessing and choosing the best option from a range of options according to a number of factors or attributes. One approach to enhance the MADM process is the utilization of similarity measures, which assess the resemblance between alternatives in a multidimensional space. These measures play a pivotal role in quantifying the degree of similarity between alternatives, providing a foundation for decision-makers to make informed and effective choices.

The idea of the IT2IFS centroid in this specific circumstance is provided and elaborated upon in this research paper. Furthermore, the paper aims to demonstrate the utility of the centroid in the comparison of two IT2IFSs using a EVSM. This comparative analysis is crucial for refining the mapping process between the CWW engine’s output and linguistic labels, enhancing the accuracy and effectiveness of linguistic comprehension in the concept of fuzzy set theory.

The arrangement of the article is as follows: A few basic descriptions are provided within Section 2. In Section 3 Centroid of IT2IFS is presented. Section 4 demonstrates the Extended Vector similarity measure. In Section 5 an application is demonstrated to represent the proposed approach.

2. Preliminaries

A few definitions are briefly reviewed in this section.

Definition 2.1. In (Mendel et al. 2002, 2006), IT2IFS $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}$ is described as

$$\tilde{\mathcal{J}} = \int_{\mathfrak{x} \in \mathfrak{J}} \int_{u \in J_{\mathfrak{x}}} \frac{1}{(\mathfrak{x}, u)} = [(\mathfrak{p}, \mathfrak{q}, \mathfrak{r}, \mathfrak{r}; \bar{\lambda}(x)), (\mathfrak{p}, \mathfrak{q}, \mathfrak{r}, \mathfrak{r}; \underline{\lambda}(x))] \tag{1}$$

The FOU of $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}$ [FOU($\tilde{\mathcal{J}}$)], that is, the union of all the primary memberships, represents uncertainty about $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}$.

$$FOU(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}) = \bigcup_{\mathfrak{x} \in \mathfrak{J}} J_{\mathfrak{x}} = \{(\mathfrak{x}, \eta) : \eta \in J_{\mathfrak{x}} = [\underline{\mathcal{J}}(\mathfrak{x}), \overline{\mathcal{J}}(\mathfrak{x})] \subseteq [0, 1]\}. \tag{2}$$

FIGURE 1. IT2FS

Definition 2.2. An IFS $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}$ has the form $\tilde{\mathcal{J}} = ([\mathfrak{p}, \mathfrak{q}, \mathfrak{r}, \mathfrak{r}]; \lambda_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}}, \eta_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}})$ where its trapezoidal membership function $\lambda_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}}(\mathfrak{x})$ is described as follows:

$$\lambda_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}}(\mathfrak{x}) = \begin{cases} \frac{(\mathfrak{x}-\mathfrak{p})h_{\lambda_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}}}}{\mathfrak{q}-\mathfrak{p}} & \mathfrak{p} \leq \mathfrak{x} < \mathfrak{q} \\ h_{\lambda_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}}} & \mathfrak{q} \leq \mathfrak{x} \leq \mathfrak{r} \\ \frac{(\mathfrak{r}-\mathfrak{x})h_{\lambda_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}}}}{\mathfrak{r}-\mathfrak{r}} & \mathfrak{r} \leq \mathfrak{x} < \mathfrak{r} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

$$\eta_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}}(\mathfrak{x}) = \begin{cases} \frac{(\mathfrak{q}-\mathfrak{x})+h_{\eta_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}}(\mathfrak{x}-\mathfrak{p})}}{\mathfrak{q}-\mathfrak{p}} & \mathfrak{p} \leq \mathfrak{x} < \mathfrak{q} \\ h_{\eta_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}}} & \mathfrak{q} \leq \mathfrak{x} \leq \mathfrak{r} \\ \frac{(\mathfrak{x}-\mathfrak{r})+h_{\eta_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}}(\mathfrak{r}-\mathfrak{x})}}{\mathfrak{r}-\mathfrak{r}} & \mathfrak{r} \leq \mathfrak{x} < \mathfrak{r} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where $h_{\lambda_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}}}$ and $h_{\eta_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}}}$ are heights of the MF and NMF satisfying $0 \leq h_{\lambda_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}}} \leq 1$, $0 \leq h_{\eta_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}}} \leq 1$, $0 \leq h_{\lambda_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}}} + h_{\eta_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}}} \leq 1$, and $\mathfrak{p}, \mathfrak{q}, \mathfrak{r}, \mathfrak{r} \in \tilde{\mathcal{J}}$.

Definition 2.3. In IT2IFS (Yuan and Chao 2019), the type-1 membership is the ordinary fuzzy membership with additional membership as well as NMF. An IT2ITrFS $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}$ is stated as:

$$\tilde{\mathcal{J}} = \int_{\mathfrak{x} \in \mathcal{J}} \int_{\mathfrak{u} \in J_{\mathfrak{x}}^{\lambda}} \int_{\mathfrak{u} \in J_{\mathfrak{x}}^{\eta}} \frac{1}{(\mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{u})} = \int_{\mathfrak{x} \in \mathcal{J}} \left[\int_{\mathfrak{u} \in J_{\mathfrak{x}}^{\lambda}} \int_{\mathfrak{u} \in J_{\mathfrak{x}}^{\eta}} \frac{1}{\mathfrak{u}} \right] / \mathfrak{x} \quad (5)$$

It's lower and upper membership $[\lambda_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}}(\mathfrak{x}), \bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}}(\mathfrak{x})]$ and non-membership functions $[\eta_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}}(\mathfrak{x}), \bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}}(\mathfrak{x})]$ are as:

$$\lambda_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}}(\mathfrak{x}) = \begin{cases} \frac{(\mathfrak{x}-\mathfrak{p})h_{\lambda_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}}}}{\mathfrak{q}-\mathfrak{p}} & \mathfrak{p} \leq \mathfrak{x} < \mathfrak{q} \\ h_{\lambda_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}}} & \mathfrak{q} \leq \mathfrak{x} \leq \mathfrak{r} \\ \frac{(\mathfrak{r}-\mathfrak{x})h_{\lambda_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}}}}{\mathfrak{r}-\mathfrak{r}} & \mathfrak{r} \leq \mathfrak{x} < \mathfrak{r} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

$$\bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}}(\mathfrak{x}) = \begin{cases} \frac{(\mathfrak{x}-\mathfrak{p})h_{\bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}}}}{\mathfrak{q}-\mathfrak{p}} & \mathfrak{p} \leq \mathfrak{x} < \mathfrak{q} \\ h_{\bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}}} & \mathfrak{q} \leq \mathfrak{x} \leq \mathfrak{r} \\ \frac{(\mathfrak{r}-\mathfrak{x})h_{\bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}}}}{\mathfrak{r}-\mathfrak{r}} & \mathfrak{r} \leq \mathfrak{x} < \mathfrak{r} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

$$\eta_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}}(\mathfrak{x}) = \begin{cases} \frac{(\mathfrak{q}-\mathfrak{x})+h_{\eta_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}}(\mathfrak{x}-\mathfrak{p})}}{\mathfrak{q}-\mathfrak{p}} & \mathfrak{p} \leq \mathfrak{x} < \mathfrak{q} \\ h_{\eta_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}}} & \mathfrak{q} \leq \mathfrak{x} \leq \mathfrak{r} \\ \frac{(\mathfrak{x}-\mathfrak{r})+h_{\eta_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}}(\mathfrak{r}-\mathfrak{x})}}{\mathfrak{r}-\mathfrak{r}} & \mathfrak{r} \leq \mathfrak{x} < \mathfrak{r} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

$$\bar{\eta}_{\tilde{J}}(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{(\acute{q}-x)+h\bar{\eta}_{\tilde{J}}(x-\acute{p})}{\acute{q}-\acute{p}} & \acute{p} \leq x < \acute{q} \\ h\bar{\eta}_{\tilde{J}} & \acute{q} \leq x \leq \acute{t} \\ \frac{(x-\acute{t})+h\bar{\eta}_{\tilde{J}}(\acute{t}-x)}{\acute{t}-\acute{t}} & \acute{t} \leq x < \acute{t} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

Uncertainty is represented as the *FOU* of $\tilde{J}$,

$$\begin{aligned} FOU_{\lambda}(\tilde{J}) &= \bigcup_{x \in \mathcal{J}} J_x^{\lambda} \\ &= \{(x, \eta) : \eta \in J_x = [\underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{J}}(x), \bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{J}}(x)] \subseteq [0, 1]\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} FOU_{\eta}(\tilde{J}) &= \bigcup_{x \in \mathcal{J}} J_x^{\eta} \\ &= \{(x, \eta) : \eta \in J_x = [\underline{\eta}_{\tilde{J}}(x), \bar{\eta}_{\tilde{J}}(x)] \subseteq [0, 1]\}. \end{aligned}$$

where $0 \leq h_{\underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{J}}} \leq 1$, $0 \leq h_{\bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{J}}} \leq 1$, $0 \leq h_{\underline{\eta}_{\tilde{J}}} \leq 1$, $0 \leq h_{\bar{\eta}_{\tilde{J}}} \leq 1$, $0 \leq h_{\underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{J}}} + h_{\bar{\eta}_{\tilde{J}}} \leq 1$, $0 \leq h_{\bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{J}}} + h_{\underline{\eta}_{\tilde{J}}} \leq 1$, and $\acute{p}, \acute{q}, \acute{t}, \acute{r} \in \mathbb{R}$.

The IT2ITrFN is denoted as $\tilde{J} = \langle ([\acute{p}, \acute{q}, \acute{t}, \acute{r}]; \bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{J}}, \underline{\eta}_{\tilde{J}}), ([\acute{p}, \acute{q}, \acute{t}, \acute{r}]; \lambda_{\tilde{J}}, \bar{\eta}_{\tilde{J}}) \rangle$.

FIGURE 2. IT2ITrFS

Definition 2.4. The weight w and the centroid c of a FS $\tilde{J} = (\mathcal{J}, \lambda)$ are described as follows:

$$w = \int \lambda(x) dx \quad (10)$$

and

$$c = \frac{\int x \lambda(x) dx}{\int \lambda(x) dx} \quad (11)$$

Definition 2.5. The centroid $C_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}}$ of IT2FS, given an IT2FS with an embedded T1FS $\mathcal{J}_\lambda$, $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}$ is the union of all $\mathcal{J}_\lambda$ centroids (Wu and Mendel 2007).

$$C_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}} = \bigcup_{\forall \mathcal{J}_\lambda} c(\mathcal{J}_\lambda) = \bigcup_{\forall \mathcal{J}_\lambda} \frac{\int_{\mathcal{J}} \mathbf{x} \lambda_{\mathcal{J}_\lambda}(\mathbf{x}) dx}{\int_{\mathcal{J}} \lambda_{\mathcal{J}_\lambda}(\mathbf{x}) dx} = [c_l(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}), c_r(\tilde{\mathcal{J}})] \quad (12)$$

where the centroid of $\mathcal{J}_\lambda$ is $c(\mathcal{J}_\lambda)$, and for every $\mathcal{J}_\lambda$, the centroid with the lowest value is $c_l(\tilde{\mathcal{J}})$, and the centroid with the highest value is $c_r(\tilde{\mathcal{J}})$. Using the KM algorithm (Liu and Mendel 2008), $c_l(\tilde{\mathcal{J}})$ and $c_r(\tilde{\mathcal{J}})$ may be calculated.

Definition 2.6. A similarity measure s must satisfies the following for any fuzzy sets $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_3$:

- (1) **Reflexivity:** If and only if two fuzzy sets (FSs) are exact identical, then their similarity is 1, expressed as $s(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2) = 1 \Leftrightarrow \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1 = \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2$.
- (2) **Symmetry:** The order of computation should not affect the similarity between two FSs; in other words, $s(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2)$ should be the same as $s(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1)$.
- (3) **Monotonicity:** As the distance between two FSs increases, their similarity decreases. If $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1 \subseteq \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2 \subseteq \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_3$, then $s(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_3) \leq s(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2)$ and $s(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_3) \leq s(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_3)$.
- (4) **Overlapping:** If the intersection of two fuzzy sets is non-empty, there should be some level of similarity between them. This can be expressed as follows: if $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1 \cap \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2 \neq \emptyset \Rightarrow s(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2) > 0$.

Definition 2.7. In (Wu and Mendel 2007), it has been described that assessing the resemblance among IT2FSs $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2$, it is crucial to consider both their shapes and proximity. The VSM for IT2FSs, stated by Wu and Mendel, comprises two components, namely,

$$s_{vsm}(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2) = (s_1(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2), s_2(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2))^T \quad (13)$$

where the degree of similarity between each of the shapes of $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2$ is represented by $s_1(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2) \in [0, 1]$, and $s_2(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2) \in [0, 1]$. s_1 is a metric of similarity between $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2$ in terms of their distance. To compute $s_1(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2)$, $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2$ are *aligned* for shape comparison. Denote the centroids of $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2$ as $C_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1} = [c_l(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1), c_r(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1)]$ and $C_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2} = [c_l(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2), c_r(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2)]$, respectively. The centers of $C_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}$ and $C_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}$ are defined as

$$c(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1) = \frac{[c_l(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1), c_r(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1)]}{2}$$

$$c(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2) = \frac{[c_l(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2), c_r(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2)]}{2}$$

Moving $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2$ so that $c(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1)$ and $c(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2)$ coincide is a suitable alignment procedure. When $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2$ are aligned, $s_1(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2)$ is defined as,

$$s_1(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2) = \frac{AC(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1 \cap \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2')}{AC(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1 \cup \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2')} = \frac{\text{card}(\bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}(\mathbf{x}) \cap \bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2'}(\mathbf{x}) + \text{card}(\underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}(\mathbf{x}) \cap \underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2'}(\mathbf{x}))}{\text{card}(\bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}(\mathbf{x}) \cup \bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2'}(\mathbf{x}) + \text{card}(\underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}(\mathbf{x}) \cup \underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2'}(\mathbf{x}))} \quad (14)$$

where $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2'$ is $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2$ moved to $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1$.

$s_2(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2)$ gauges the proximity of $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2$, and it is defined as

$$s_2(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2) = h(d(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2)) \quad (15)$$

where

$$d(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2) = |c(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1) - c(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2)| \quad (16)$$

is the Euclidean distance among the respective centers of the centroids of $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1$ as well as $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2$, while h may correspond to any function satisfying: A monotonic reduction in $h(\mathbf{x})$ occurs as $\mathbf{x}$ increases, (2) $h(\mathbf{x}) = 1 \iff \mathbf{x} = 0$, and (3) $\lim_{\mathbf{x} \rightarrow \infty} h(\mathbf{x}) = 0$.

3. Centroid of IT2IFS

A fuzzy set's centroid is an essential metric, providing a representative point that summarizes the central tendency of the set's membership distribution. In the realm of IT2IFS (IT2IFS), the centroid becomes an even more intricate concept, capturing not only the uncertainty in membership but also the intuitionistic hesitation associated with each element.

Each element in an IT2IFS has a membership interval as well as a non-membership interval, providing a more thorough depiction of uncertainty. The degree of hesitation or uncertainty in the process of making choices is taken into account by the intuitionistic component, which adds another level of complexity.

An IT2IFS's centroid involves the calculation of a representative point within the combined uncertainty space defined by both the membership and non-membership intervals. This representative point not only considers the central tendency of the membership distribution but also incorporates the nuances introduced by the intuitionistic factor.

In mathematical terms, the centroid of an IT2IFS is established by a weighted average that takes into account the intuitionistic component as well as traditional membership and non-membership degrees. Resulting centroid provides a valuable insight into the central tendency of the fuzzy set while accounting for the multifaceted nature of uncertainty inherent in complex decision-making scenarios.

In the subsequent definition, we provide the formal expression for computing the centroid of an IT2IFS, clarifying each element's contribution to encapsulating the core of ambiguity in the set. Let $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_\lambda$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_\eta$ be an embedded type-2 MF and NMF of an IT2IFS $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}$. The centroids

of MF and NMF of $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}$ are defined as:

$$C_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}}^{\lambda} = \bigcup_{\forall \mathcal{J}_{\lambda}} c(\mathcal{J}_{\lambda}) = \bigcup_{\forall \mathcal{J}_{\lambda}} \frac{\int_{\mathcal{J}} \mathbf{x} \lambda_{\mathcal{J}_{\lambda}}(\mathbf{x}) dx}{\int_{\mathcal{J}} \lambda_{\mathcal{J}_{\lambda}}(\mathbf{x}) dx} = [c_l^{\lambda}(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}), c_r^{\lambda}(\tilde{\mathcal{J}})] \quad (17)$$

where

$$c_l^{\lambda}(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k x_i \bar{\lambda}_{\mathcal{J}_{\lambda}} + \sum_{i=k+1}^L x_i \underline{\lambda}_{\mathcal{J}_{\lambda}}}{\sum_{i=1}^k \bar{\lambda}_{\mathcal{J}_{\lambda}} + \sum_{i=k+1}^L \underline{\lambda}_{\mathcal{J}_{\lambda}}} \quad (18)$$

$$c_r^{\lambda}(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k x_i \underline{\lambda}_{\mathcal{J}_{\lambda}} + \sum_{i=k+1}^R x_i \bar{\lambda}_{\mathcal{J}_{\lambda}}}{\sum_{i=1}^k \underline{\lambda}_{\mathcal{J}_{\lambda}} + \sum_{i=k+1}^R \bar{\lambda}_{\mathcal{J}_{\lambda}}} \quad (19)$$

and

$$C_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}}^{\eta} = \bigcup_{\forall \mathcal{J}_{\eta}} c(\mathcal{J}_{\eta}) = \bigcup_{\forall \mathcal{J}_{\eta}} \frac{\int_{\mathcal{J}} \mathbf{x} \eta_{\mathcal{J}_{\eta}}(\mathbf{x}) dx}{\int_{\mathcal{J}} \eta_{\mathcal{J}_{\eta}}(\mathbf{x}) dx} = [c_l^{\eta}(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}), c_r^{\eta}(\tilde{\mathcal{J}})] \quad (20)$$

where

$$c_l^{\eta}(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k x_i \underline{\eta}_{\mathcal{J}_{\eta}} + \sum_{i=k+1}^L x_i \bar{\eta}_{\mathcal{J}_{\eta}}}{\sum_{i=1}^k \underline{\eta}_{\mathcal{J}_{\eta}} + \sum_{i=k+1}^L \bar{\eta}_{\mathcal{J}_{\eta}}} \quad (21)$$

$$c_r^{\eta}(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k x_i \bar{\eta}_{\mathcal{J}_{\eta}} + \sum_{i=k+1}^R x_i \underline{\eta}_{\mathcal{J}_{\eta}}}{\sum_{i=1}^k \bar{\eta}_{\mathcal{J}_{\eta}} + \sum_{i=k+1}^R \underline{\eta}_{\mathcal{J}_{\eta}}} \quad (22)$$

where k is the switch point.

4. Extended Vector Similarity Measure for IT2IFS

Within the context of IT2IFS, assessing similarity goes beyond a straightforward comparison of shapes; it necessitates a comprehensive evaluation of both form and the distance. The *Extended Vector Similarity Measure* (EVSM) in context of IT2IFS, encapsulates this dual perspective by decomposing the overall similarity into two components.

The EVSM is expressed as a vector $S_{EVSM}(\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2)$, where each component serves a distinct purpose. The first component, $s_1(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2)$, quantifies the similarity in shape between the IT2IFSs $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2$. This shape-based similarity takes into account the alignment of the sets, ensuring a meaningful comparison. The second component, $s_2(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2)$, focuses on the proximity of $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2$, measuring how closely they are positioned in the fuzzy space. The vector similarity measure is expressed as:

$$S_{EVSM}(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2) = (s_1(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2), s_2(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2))^T$$

where $s_1(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2)$ and $s_2(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2)$ are both confined to the interval $[0, 1]$.

To compute s_1 , a crucial step involves aligning $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2$ by adjusting their positions in a manner that their centroids coincide. This alignment facilitates the comparison of their

shapes. $s_1(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2)$ is then computed as the ratio of the average cardinality of UMF, LMF, UNMF, and LNMF intersection to the average cardinality of corresponding unions.

$$\begin{aligned}
s_1(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2) &= \frac{AC(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1 \cap \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2')}{AC(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1 \cup \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2')} \\
&= \frac{\text{card}(\bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}(\mathfrak{x}) \cap \bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2'}(\mathfrak{x})) + \text{card}(\underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}(\mathfrak{x}) \cap \underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2'}(\mathfrak{x})) + \text{card}(\bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}(\mathfrak{x}) \cap \bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2'}(\mathfrak{x})) + \text{card}(\underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}(\mathfrak{x}) \cap \underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2'}(\mathfrak{x}))}{\text{card}(\bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}(\mathfrak{x}) \cup \bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2'}(\mathfrak{x})) + \text{card}(\underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}(\mathfrak{x}) \cup \underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2'}(\mathfrak{x})) + \text{card}(\bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}(\mathfrak{x}) \cup \bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2'}(\mathfrak{x})) + \text{card}(\underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}(\mathfrak{x}) \cup \underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2'}(\mathfrak{x}))} \\
&= \frac{\int_{\mathcal{J}} \min(\bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}(\mathfrak{x}), \bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2'}(\mathfrak{x}))dx + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \min(\underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}(\mathfrak{x}), \underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2'}(\mathfrak{x}))dx + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \min(\bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}(\mathfrak{x}), \bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2'}(\mathfrak{x}))dx + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \min(\underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}(\mathfrak{x}), \underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2'}(\mathfrak{x}))dx}{\int_{\mathcal{J}} \max(\bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}(\mathfrak{x}), \bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2'}(\mathfrak{x}))dx + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \max(\underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}(\mathfrak{x}), \underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2'}(\mathfrak{x}))dx + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \max(\bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}(\mathfrak{x}), \bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2'}(\mathfrak{x}))dx + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \max(\underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}(\mathfrak{x}), \underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2'}(\mathfrak{x}))dx} \quad (23)
\end{aligned}$$

where $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2'$ is $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2$ that has been moved to $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1$.

The second component, $s_2(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2)$, assesses the proximity between $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2$, the Euclidean distance that lies between the centers from $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1$ to $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2$ determines it, denoted as $d(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2)$. The function h further scales this distance, adhering to specific properties.

$$s_2(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2) = h(d(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2)) \quad (24)$$

where

$$d(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2) = |c(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1) - c(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2)|$$

Any function satisfying the following can be h . (1) monotonic reduction in $h(\mathfrak{x})$ occurs as $\mathfrak{x}$ increases, (2) $h(\mathfrak{x}) = 1 \iff \mathfrak{x} = 0$, and (3) $\lim_{\mathfrak{x} \rightarrow \infty} h(\mathfrak{x}) = 0$. The extended vector similarity measure, therefore, provides a nuanced evaluation of the similarity between IT2IFSs, accounting for both their shapes and proximity. This comprehensive approach enables a more robust comparison, making it a valuable tool in decision-making processes where uncertainty is inherent.

Theorem 4.1. *The EVSM meets the requirements for reflexivity, symmetry, monotonicity and overlapping.*

Proof. (1) **Reflexivity:** To show that S_{EVSM} is reflexive, let us suppose that $S_{EVSM}(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2) = 1 \iff \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1 = \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2$.

The only way that $S_{EVSM}(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2) = 1$ is possible when $\min(\bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}, \bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}) = \max(\bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}, \bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2})$, $\min(\underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}, \underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}) = \max(\underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}, \underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2})$, $\min(\bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}, \bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}) = \max(\bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}, \bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2})$ and $\min(\underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}, \underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}) = \max(\underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}, \underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2})$, which implies that $\bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1} = \bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}$, $\underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1} = \underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}$, $\bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1} = \bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}$ and $\underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1} = \underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}$ which shows that $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1 = \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2$.

Conversely, $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1 = \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2$ means that $\bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1} = \bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}$, $\underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1} = \underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}$, $\bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1} = \bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}$ and $\underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1} = \underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}$ which implies that $\min(\bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}, \bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}) = \max(\bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}, \bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2})$, $\min(\underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}, \underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}) = \max(\underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}, \underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2})$, $\min(\bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}, \bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}) = \max(\bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}, \bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2})$ and $\min(\underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}, \underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}) = \max(\underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}, \underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2})$, which follows that $S_{EVSM}(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2) = 1$

(2) **Symmetry:** Symmetry of S_{EVSM} is obvious as $S_{EVSM}(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2)$ does not rely on the sequence in which $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2$ so $S_{EVSM}(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2) = S_{EVSM}(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1)$

(3) **Monotonicity:** Let $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1 \subseteq \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2 \subseteq \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_3$, then

$$S_{EVSM}(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2) = \frac{\int_{\mathcal{J}} \min(\bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}(\mathfrak{r}), \bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}(\mathfrak{r}))dx + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \min(\underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}(\mathfrak{r}), \underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}(\mathfrak{r}))dx + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \min(\bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}(\mathfrak{r}), \bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}(\mathfrak{r}))dx + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \min(\underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}(\mathfrak{r}), \underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}(\mathfrak{r}))dx}{\int_{\mathcal{J}} \max(\bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}(\mathfrak{r}), \bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}(\mathfrak{r}))dx + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \max(\underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}(\mathfrak{r}), \underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}(\mathfrak{r}))dx + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \max(\bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}(\mathfrak{r}), \bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}(\mathfrak{r}))dx + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \max(\underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}(\mathfrak{r}), \underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}(\mathfrak{r}))dx} \quad (25)$$

$$S_{EVSM}(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2) = \frac{\int_{\mathcal{J}} \bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1} + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1} + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1} + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}}{\int_{\mathcal{J}} \bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2} + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2} + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2} + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}} \quad (26)$$

$$S_{EVSM}(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_3) = \frac{\int_{\mathcal{J}} \min(\bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}(\mathfrak{r}), \bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{C}}}(\mathfrak{r}))dx + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \min(\underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}(\mathfrak{r}), \underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{C}}}(\mathfrak{r}))dx + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \min(\bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}(\mathfrak{r}), \bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{C}}}(\mathfrak{r}))dx + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \min(\underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}(\mathfrak{r}), \underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{C}}}(\mathfrak{r}))dx}{\int_{\mathcal{J}} \max(\bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}(\mathfrak{r}), \bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{C}}}(\mathfrak{r}))dx + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \max(\underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}(\mathfrak{r}), \underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{C}}}(\mathfrak{r}))dx + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \max(\bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}(\mathfrak{r}), \bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{C}}}(\mathfrak{r}))dx + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \max(\underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}(\mathfrak{r}), \underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{C}}}(\mathfrak{r}))dx} \quad (27)$$

$$S_{EVSM}(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_3) = \frac{\int_{\mathcal{J}} \bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1} + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1} + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1} + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}}{\int_{\mathcal{J}} \bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_3} + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_3} + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_3} + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_3}} \quad (28)$$

because $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2 \subseteq \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_3$, it follows that $\int_{\mathcal{J}} \bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2} + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2} + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2} + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2} \leq \int_{\mathcal{J}} \bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_3} + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_3} + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_3} + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_3}$, hence $S_{EVSM}(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2) \geq S_{EVSM}(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_3)$. Similarly it can be shown that $S_{EVSM}(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_3) \geq S_{EVSM}(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_3)$

(4) **Overlapping:** If $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1 \cap \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2 \neq \emptyset$, $\exists \mathfrak{r}$ such that $\min(\bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}$ and $\bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}) > 0$, $\min(\bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}, \bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}) > 0$, then the numerator of (23),

$$\int_{\mathcal{J}} \min(\bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}, \bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}) + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \min(\underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}, \underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}) + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \min(\bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}, \bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}) + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \min(\underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}, \underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}) > 0 \quad (29)$$

In the denominator of (23),

$$\int_{\mathcal{J}} \max(\bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}, \bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}) + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \max(\underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}, \underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}) + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \max(\bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}, \bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}) + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \max(\underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}, \underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}) \geq \int_{\mathcal{J}} \min(\bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}, \bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}) + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \min(\underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}, \underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}) + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \min(\bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}, \bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}) + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \min(\underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}, \underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}) > 0 \quad (30)$$

Consequently, $S_{EVSM}(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2) > 0$. On the other hand, when $S_{EVSM}(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2) = 0$, then $\min(\bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}, \bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}) = \min(\underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}, \underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}) = \min(\bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}, \bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}) = \min(\underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}, \underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}) = 0 \forall \mathfrak{r}$, then in the numerator of (23)

$$\int_{\mathcal{J}} \min(\bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}, \bar{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}) + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \min(\underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}, \underline{\lambda}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}) + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \min(\bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}, \bar{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}) + \int_{\mathcal{J}} \min(\underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1}, \underline{\eta}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2}) = 0$$

consequently, Consequently, $S_{EVSM}(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_1, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_2) = 0$.

0.1cm□

5. Application

This section presents examples pertaining to MADM in an interval type-2 intuitionistic setting in order to show the usefulness and practicality of the suggested methodology.

5.1. Smog Control

In Lahore, persistent smog poses a significant environmental challenge, primarily stemming from vehicular emissions, industrial pollutants, and agricultural residue burning. High traffic density contributes to elevated levels of nitrogen oxides and particulate matter, while unregulated industrial emissions further worsen air quality. The practice of burning crop residues adds to the smog problem, releasing pollutants into the atmosphere. To address this issue, three potential air quality improvement measures have been considered. First, $\mathfrak{J}_1$ the introduction of electric buses aims to reduce pollutants significantly, with moderate cost-effectiveness and positive social acceptance due to heightened environmental awareness. Second, $\mathfrak{J}_2$ the implementation of stricter emission standards for industries targets a moderate reduction in pollutants, offers good cost-effectiveness over the long term, and may face initial resistance. Third, $\mathfrak{J}_3$ afforestation projects seek to improve air quality by enhancing green cover, resulting in moderate reductions in pollutants, cost-effectiveness, and high social acceptance. The key attributes for evaluation are C_1 reduction in pollutants, C_2 cost-effectiveness, and C_3 social acceptance. To determine the most suitable solution, EVSM using IT2IFS will be employed, considering the uncertainties associated with each attribute value for a comprehensive decision-making process.

	C_1	C_2	C_3
$\mathfrak{J}_1$	[(4,6,7,9;0.1,0.9),(5,6,7,8;0.3,0.6)]	[(1,3,4,6;0.3,0.7),(2,3,4,5;0.4,0.5)]	[(2,4,5,7;0.2,0.8),(3,4,5,6;0.3,0.6)]
$\mathfrak{J}_2$	[(3,5,7,9;0.2,0.7),(4,5,7,8;0.3,0.6)]	[(4,6,7,8;0.2,0.8),(5,6,6,7;0.3,0.7)]	[(2,4,6,8;0.2,0.7),(3,4,6,7;0.3,0.5)]
$\mathfrak{J}_3$	[(5,7,8,10;0.1,0.9),(6,7,8,9;0.2,0.7)]	[(1,4,5,7;0.3,0.7),(2,4,5,6;0.4,0.5)]	[(3,5,7,9;0.2,0.8),(4,5,7,8;0.3,0.7)]

TABLE 1. IT2IFS based decision matrix

We compare the alternative values on the criterias with the ideal solution $\mathfrak{J}^* = [(5, 7, 8, 10; 0, 1), (6, 7, 8, 9; 0, 0.9)]$.

In conclusion, the comprehensive evaluation of air quality improvement measures for Lahore, considering the pivotal criteria of pollutants reduction, cost-effectiveness, and social acceptance, reveals that "afforestation projects" emerge as the most suitable solution. The implementation of afforestation projects is anticipated to yield moderate reductions in pollutants, presenting a harmonious balance with favorable cost-effectiveness and high levels of social acceptance. This result underscores the importance of not only addressing environmental

	C_1	C_2	C_3
$\tilde{J}_1$	0.9588	0.4725	0.3729
$\tilde{J}_2$	0.9113	0.5265	0.5821
$\tilde{J}_3$	0.9657	0.4825	0.9836
Ranking order	$\tilde{J}_3 > \tilde{J}_1 > \tilde{J}_2$	$\tilde{J}_2 > \tilde{J}_3 > \tilde{J}_1$	$\tilde{J}_3 > \tilde{J}_2 > \tilde{J}_1$

TABLE 2. Decision matrix on applying EVSM

FIGURE 3. Comparison of $\tilde{J}_1$, $\tilde{J}_2$ and $\tilde{J}_3$ on the basis of C_1

FIGURE 4. Comparison of $\tilde{J}_1$, $\tilde{J}_2$ and $\tilde{J}_3$ on the basis of C_2

concerns through pollutant reduction but also considering the economic viability and societal approval of the chosen measure. Afforestation, with its potential to enhance green cover and contribute to the city’s ecological health, stands out as the optimal choice in mitigating the pervasive smog issue in Lahore. This decision not only aligns with ecological sustainability but also acknowledges the social dynamics and economic considerations crucial for the successful implementation of air quality improvement initiatives.

FIGURE 5. Comparison of $\tilde{I}_1$, $\tilde{I}_2$ and $\tilde{I}_3$ on the basis of C_1

6. Conclusion

In conclusion, this paper has delved into the intricacies of the centroid computation for IT2IFS and provided a comprehensive exploration of the EVSM applied to IT2IFS. By establishing a clear understanding of these mathematical concepts, we have showcased their potential in addressing real-world challenges. The practical application of EVSM in controlling smog in Lahore serves as a noteworthy example, demonstrating the versatility and effectiveness of these methods. As we navigate the complexities of environmental issues, the knowledge gathered from this study can help create solid plans and tactics for handling and lessening environmental problems on a larger scale. The integration of theoretical foundations with practical applications underscores the significance of bridging the gap between academic knowledge and real-world problem-solving, highlighting the potential for continued advancements in the realm of fuzzy logic and environmental control.

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7. Ethical Approval

Not applicable.

8. Consent to Participate

Not applicable.

9. Consent to Publish

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10. Authors Contributions

Touqeer conceived and designed the analysis of the proposed scheme. Sajeela has worked out the Mathematical models and wrote the paper.

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The authors declare that they have no competing interests.